

MBD Free Project

INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR COMPARING OLD BUILDING IN KIVUNGE

Part 1. Greetings and introduction

Hello, my name is _____. I am an _____ and researcher based in _____.

I'm part of the MBD-Free Project, which looks at how hospital buildings and their surroundings can be improved to reduce mosquito-borne diseases. In this interview, we'd like to gather your feedback about the new outdoor waiting areas and planting. There are no right or wrong answers, we just want your honest experiences and opinions.

Part 2. Confidentiality

I'd like to record this interview to make sure I capture your answers accurately. Everything you share will be kept confidential and used only for research. We won't include your name or any identifying details in our reports. The results from this interview may be published, but always in a way that does not identify you. Your input will help us develop better strategies to protect hospital users from mosquito-borne diseases.

Are you comfortable to continue?

Part 3. Interview questions

Main Question
Use and general perceptions
1. How would you describe the new outdoor waiting and green areas in your own words?
2. How often do you see or use these spaces during a typical day? Who tends to use them the most — patients, visitors, or staff?
3. What kinds of activities do people usually do there (e.g., waiting, resting, socializing)?
4. What do you like most about these areas? Are there any aspects you find less helpful?
Changes in the main indoor waiting areas
5. Since the outdoor areas were created, have you noticed any difference in the number of people or the atmosphere in the main indoor waiting areas? And are there any times of the day when this is most noticeable?
6. Has there been any change in noise levels, crowding, or general comfort indoors?
7. From your perspective, how have these changes affected staff work or patient experience?
Maintenance and upkeep
8. How are these green and outdoor areas maintained and who is responsible for their care?
9. Are maintenance routines (watering, cleaning, pruning, waste removal) manageable with current staff and resources?
10. Have you encountered any challenges with maintenance or safety in these areas?
11. Have you noticed any issues with mosquitoes in these new spaces?

Benefits, Drawbacks and Improvements
12. what do you see as the main benefits of these new spaces?
13. Are there any drawbacks, problems, or unintended effects you've observed?
14. How do you think patients and visitors feel about these spaces overall?
15. What do you think could make these spaces work even better for patients, visitors, or staff?

Part 4. Interview closing statement and thank you.

Thank you very much for your participation in this interview and we look forward to discussing with you again as we progress with this intervention.